

RESEARCH ON THE APPLICATION OF GRAMMAR TRANSLATION METHOD IN CHINESE TEACHING. TAKING THE TEACHING PRACTICE OF THE CONFUCIUS INSTITUTE IN SAMARKAND AS AN EXAMPLE

Liu Xianjun

Master of Teaching Chinese to Speakers of Other Languages, Confucius Institute at Samarkand
State Institute of Foreign Languages, Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *Based on the objective evaluation on the grammar translation method, this article discusses the application direction of the grammar translation method in Chinese teaching in Uzbekistan from the perspective of Chinese teachers in China, taking the HSK intermediate and advanced courses of the Confucius Institute at the Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages as an example and conditions. It can be seen from the discussion that the grammar translation method still plays an advantage in international Chinese teaching, but it needs to be used appropriately according to specific conditions.*

Keywords: *Grammar Translation Method, HSK Intermediate and Advanced Courses, Chinese Teaching in Uzbekistan.*

1. Introduction

In second language teaching methods, integration has become the main trend in the development of teaching methods. Teaching methods show scientific comprehensiveness in the application of teaching theories and teaching forms. As an ancient and influential teaching method, the grammar translation method has its own value and advantages. Many scholars evaluate it in an objective manner (*He Rui, 1998; Cheng Chunjun, 2014; Zhang Jie, 2019; Lu Xue, 2023*), It is emphasized that actual teaching characteristics should be combined with different second language teaching methods to achieve the best teaching effect.

Based on the existing discussion, this article takes the HSK3 to HSK5 level regular courses and pre-examination tutoring classes taught by the author at the Confucius Institute at the Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages as examples to explain the application direction and principles of the grammar translation method in Chinese teaching in Uzbekistan, in order to provide a broader idea when using the translation method in later Chinese teaching.

2. Application direction of grammar translation method in Chinese teaching

2.1. Application of grammar translation method in grammar teaching

Firstly, the grammar translation method can be used for students' understanding of Chinese grammar expertise. Take the "associated words" that connect two clauses as an example. Different "associated words" express different semantic relationships and logic. For Confucius Institute students preparing for the HSK4 exam, the correct ordering and use of associated words is still a problem. Although teachers can usually teach students the semantic and logical relationships between clauses through pictures and scenarios, there is no guarantee that all students can understand.

As a Chinese teacher, although I cannot fully explain the grammatical meaning of associated words in Uzbek like native teachers, I can find Uzbek sentences that have similar grammatical meaning to the example sentences to enhance students' understanding of the relationship between different complex sentences. For example, for the sentence pattern "if....., then....." that appears in HSK level 3 and expresses a hypothetical relationship, you can use an Uzbek proverb to confirm whether students understand the concept of "hypothetical relationship":

Yurtda odam bo'lmasa, To'ng'iz tepaga chiqar. (*If the land is empty, let the wild boars go upstairs*)

Teacher can show the above proverb when explaining so that students can more accurately understand the "hypothetical relationship" in the sentence. Teacher can also use this proverb to let students determine whether it is a "hypothetical relationship" after learn "If..., (Subject) then..." , or test whether students have mastered this sentence by translating the proverb in Chinese.

Secondly, by comparing students' native language with Chinese, teachers can discover the differences between the two languages and understand the reasons why students make mistakes. For example, Chinese is in SVO word order and Uzbek is in SOV word order. students are easy be influenced by their mother tongue when expressing Chinese. For example, when the author asked "Do you like to eat sumalak?", a HSK level 3 student answered: "I like to eat sumalak", and in Uzbek this word order is established: "men Sumalak Yeyishni Yaxshikoraman".

2.2. Application of grammar translation method in vocabulary teaching

The comparison between Uzbek and Chinese can also be used in vocabulary teaching, because students' word use will be influenced by their native language. In the HSK5 level course, a student suddenly asked whether the phrase "包饺子" could be replaced by "折叠饺子". Later, the author learned that there are "Barak bukish" and "chuchvara bukish" in Uzbek, which translated into Chinese are It means "折叠饺子", but this expression is not appropriate in Chinese. If teachers understand the corresponding Uzbek translation when teaching Chinese phrases, they can use the grammar translation method to correct students' errors in their output in a targeted manner and increase students' accuracy in word usage.

In addition, there are many synonyms that need to be analyzed in the HSK5 course. Many synonyms are easily confused by students. The grammar translation method can more efficiently solve the problems students encounter when learning synonyms. For example, when distinguishing between "包含" and "包括", teacher can use the corresponding Uzbek language for translation. The content following "o'z ichiga olmoq" (包含) in Uzbek is more abstract, "o'z ichiga kiritmoq" (包括) what follows is more specific content.

However, due to the different number of synonyms and different meaning coverage in the two languages, sometimes the number of Uzbek words corresponding to Chinese synonyms is also inconsistent during mutual translation. Therefore, due to the negative transfer of mother tongue, students can easily confuse synonyms in Chinese. Taking "抱怨", "埋怨" and "责怪" as an example, the three verbal synonyms correspond to only one Uzbek verb "noroz bo'lmoq". Through the comparison of Chinese and Uzbek translations, students can be guided to further learn the usage rules of the three Chinese verbs. It can also remind teachers to emphasize the different semantic and functional combinations of these three words.

2.3. Application of grammar translation method in cultural teaching

In teaching, sometimes Chinese traditional cultural festivals suddenly happen. If teachers want to take advantage of this opportunity to supplement Chinese cultural knowledge for HSK level 3 students, they need to use translation methods to let students have a more comprehensive and profound understanding of Chinese culture. Taking the Chinese Lantern Festival as an example, the author intercepted video clips from China Daily's "话说中国节 (Talk about China Festival)" and Hunan Satellite TV's "中华文明之美 (The Beauty of Chinese Civilization)",

and then asked local teachers to translate the subtitles of the videos in Uzbek, edited them to show students. Finally, let students answer knowledge questions about the Lantern Festival through "guessing lantern riddles". Since students have a full understanding of the "Lantern Festival" content introduced in the video, students who are weak in Chinese can also give correct answers.

Figure1. Sample display of "Guessing Lantern Riddles" during the Lantern Festival

In addition, the text content and words of the HSK5 textbook can expand the modern Chinese culture. Take lesson 2 "留串钥匙给父母 (Leaving a bunch of keys for parents)" as an example. After students learn more names of relatives, they will introduce their family members and relatives. In contrast, the number of family members in modern Chinese society is not as large as that of Uzbekistan. Therefore, the author needs to introduce to all students the changes in China's family structure and fertility policies from the past to the present. Through Russian annotation, the students Not only understand why the author's family did not have any siblings, but also understood that Chinese fertility policy has changed."

Figure2. An introduction sample display of China's family structure and fertility policy

3. Application principles of grammar translation method in teaching

Firstly, teachers need to choose a suitable media language for translation and explanation based on their own language proficiency and student background. The grammar translation method generally emphasizes explaining and translating rules in the students' native language, which is

helpful for students to understand the abstract target language. However, most Chinese teachers are not proficient in the learners' native language. If the translation is wrong, it is easy to mislead the learners. Therefore, other media languages can be used instead. For example, HSK level 3 students are learning “帮助” and “见面”. When speaking, they often say “我帮忙他” or “我见面他”, some students master English, at this time, the author often explains in English and asks the students who understand to explain to other students.

Secondly, the grammar translation method can only solve the "understanding" aspect of Chinese learning, which is helpful for students of different levels to master the language rules, but it cannot solve the "can do" aspect. If students are allowed to use language knowledge flexibly in real and specific Chinese situations, requires more input and output of the target language. At this time, other suitable teaching methods such as the listening and speaking method, direct method, situational method, and communicative method should be combined.

In addition, for students of different levels, the proportion of grammar translation method is controlled. For beginners, they have just started to learn a new language and are rebuilding a new language system. The translation method can help them quickly learn Chinese rules and gain learning achievements and confidence. Teachers can use the translation method as the one of main methods of teaching. For intermediate and advanced level students, the translation method can help them understand the rules of Chinese in depth, but they have already learned a lot of language knowledge and language skills also need to be improved. Therefore, teachers need to control the frequency of using the translation method. For example, when introducing the "Lantern Festival", the author showed HSK5 students video clips with Chinese subtitles, and the content was richer. As for the following quiz session, since there are many new words in it, the author added translations.

Finally, the age of the students should also be taken into consideration when using the grammar translation method. At the Confucius Institute at the Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages, there are also some teenagers and younger children learning Chinese. Compared with adults, they are better at acquiring language naturally in a language environment, and have strong imitation and short-term memory. However, they do not start to acquire Chinese from a young age. In the Confucius Institute, they still focus on learning Chinese. Therefore, It is also necessary for teachers to use the translation method appropriately based on the age of the students. For example, in a classroom dominated by minors, teachers should try their best to use precise, brief and vivid translations to explain language rules. For example, when explaining tones and Chinese character radicals, they can be compared to the "hat of Pinyin" and the "key of Chinese characters" respectively.

4. Conclusion

By discussing the scope and principles of the application of grammar translation method in Chinese teaching, it can be seen that first of all, it can be used in grammar teaching, vocabulary teaching and cultural teaching; secondly, the language types mastered by teachers, student backgrounds, and differences between different languages will all affect the effectiveness of this teaching method. Therefore, the grammar-translation method is not a universal teaching method, but it still has an important impact on language learning. Therefore, its advantages should be fully utilized, instead of blindly rejected.

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